

Complete Bipartite Counterexamples and an Asymptotic Phase Diagram for Corona-Unimodality of General Position Polynomials

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Abstract

Let $\psi(G; x)$ be the general position polynomial of a graph G . Iršič, Klavžar, Rus, and Tuite asked whether unimodality of $\psi(G; x)$ is always preserved by the corona operation $G \circ K_1$. We answer this question in the negative inside the complete bipartite family. More precisely, $K_{36,51}$ has unimodal general position polynomial, whereas $K_{36,51} \circ K_1$ has a strict coefficient valley. An exhaustive exact computation proves that, up to interchanging the two partite sets, this is the unique complete bipartite example with $m + n \leq 87$ and that no such example occurs with $m + n < 87$. We also prove an asymptotic phase diagram in the slope range $1 < n/m < 2$. Inside the explicit interval

$$1.606975834863913 \dots < \alpha < 1.832120559548937 \dots,$$

there are infinitely many complete bipartite graphs $K_{m,n}$ for which $\psi(K_{m,n}; x)$ is unimodal but $\psi(K_{m,n} \circ K_1; x)$ is not. Outside this interval, and away from the two critical endpoint slopes, the corona polynomials are eventually unimodal for each fixed rational slope. The endpoints are the unique roots of two explicit entropy equations.

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1 Introduction

All graphs in this paper are finite, simple, and undirected. A set $S \subseteq V(G)$ is a *general position set* if no three vertices of S lie on a common geodesic, equivalently, no vertex of S lies on a shortest path between two other vertices of S . The *general position polynomial* is

$$\psi(G; x) = \sum_{k \geq 0} g_k(G) x^k,$$

where $g_k(G)$ denotes the number of general position sets of cardinality k . This polynomial was introduced and studied systematically by Iršič, Klavžar, Rus, and Tuite [1]. They asked whether unimodality of $\psi(G; x)$ is preserved under the corona operation $G \circ K_1$; see [1, Problem 5.1]. Rather [2] subsequently verified positive cases for several natural families and recorded the general problem as open.

We prove that the corona-unimodality question has a negative answer even for complete bipartite graphs. Our first result is the following exact smallest example inside this family.

Theorem 1. *The polynomial $\psi(K_{36,51}; x)$ is unimodal, but $\psi(K_{36,51} \circ K_1; x)$ is not unimodal. Moreover, up to interchanging the two partite sets, no complete bipartite graph $K_{m,n}$ with $m + n < 87$ has this property, and $K_{36,51}$ is the unique example with $m + n = 87$.*

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The second result shows that the example is not isolated. All logarithms are natural, and

$$\mathcal{H}(u) = -u \log u - (1 - u) \log(1 - u) \quad (0 < u < 1)$$

denotes the binary entropy function. Define

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi_-(\alpha) &= (1 + \alpha) \log(1 + \alpha) - \alpha \log \alpha + \frac{\alpha}{3} \log \frac{\alpha}{3} - \left(1 + \frac{\alpha}{3}\right) \log \left(1 + \frac{\alpha}{3}\right) - \frac{2\alpha}{3} \log 2, \\ \Phi_+(\alpha) &= (1 + \alpha) \log(1 + \alpha) - \alpha \log \alpha + \frac{\alpha - 1}{2} \log \frac{\alpha - 1}{2} - \frac{\alpha + 1}{2} \log \frac{\alpha + 1}{2} - \frac{\alpha + 1}{2} \log 2. \end{aligned}$$

Let α_- be the unique root of $\Phi_-(\alpha) = 0$ in $(1, 2)$, and let α_+ be the unique root of $\Phi_+(\alpha) = 0$ in $(1, 2)$. Numerically,

$$\alpha_- = 1.606975834863913\dots, \quad \alpha_+ = 1.832120559548937\dots$$

Theorem 2. *For every rational number $\alpha \in (\alpha_-, \alpha_+)$ there are infinitely many positive integers m for which $n = \alpha m$ is an integer and*

$$\psi(K_{m,n}; x) \quad \text{is unimodal,}$$

whereas

$$\psi(K_{m,n} \circ K_1; x) \quad \text{is not unimodal.}$$

More precisely, for infinitely many such m the coefficient sequence of $\psi(K_{m,n} \circ K_1; x)$ has a strict local valley.

The preceding result is complemented by the following asymptotic half-classification. It shows that, away from the two critical endpoint slopes, the same two entropy equations separate the eventual unimodal slopes from the slopes where strict local valleys occur infinitely often.

Theorem 3 (asymptotic phase diagram). *Let $\alpha \in \mathbb{Q}$ and $1 < \alpha < 2$.*

- (a) *If $\alpha \in (\alpha_-, \alpha_+)$, then there are infinitely many positive integers m , with $n = \alpha m$ integral, such that $\psi(K_{m,n} \circ K_1; x)$ is not unimodal.*
- (b) *If $\alpha \in (1, \alpha_-) \cup (\alpha_+, 2)$, then for all sufficiently large positive integers m with $n = \alpha m$ integral, the polynomial $\psi(K_{m,n} \circ K_1; x)$ is unimodal.*

Consequently, except for the two critical slopes α_- and α_+ , the interval (α_-, α_+) is the asymptotic non-unimodality region for complete bipartite coronas in the slope range $1 < n/m < 2$, with the caveat that part (a) asserts infinitely many strict valleys rather than a valley for every sufficiently large denominator.

Remark 1 (finite-scale convergence). *The finite computations are consistent with Theorem 3. For example, scanning $m \leq n \leq 2m$ by the exact coefficient formula, but using logarithmic arithmetic only for this numerical orientation, gives the following observed non-unimodal slope intervals:*

m	observed non-unimodal interval for n/m
100	[1.550000, 1.640000]
300	[1.590000, 1.756667]
1000	[1.602000, 1.805000]
2000	[1.604500, 1.817000]
5000	[1.606000, 1.825400].

These intervals approach the theoretical endpoints $1.6069758348\dots$ and $1.8321205595\dots$. The table is not used in the proof.

2 Complete bipartite graphs

We use the convention that $\binom{a}{b} = 0$ when $b < 0$ or $b > a$.

Lemma 1. For $m, n \geq 1$, with $N = m + n$,

$$\psi(K_{m,n}; x) = 1 + Nx + \binom{N}{2}x^2 + \sum_{k=3}^{\max\{m,n\}} \left(\binom{m}{k} + \binom{n}{k} \right) x^k.$$

Proof. Every set of size at most 2 is a general position set. Let A and B be the partite sets. If S has size at least 3 and meets both A and B , then S contains two vertices from one part and one vertex from the other part; the latter vertex lies on a shortest path between the former two. Hence every general position set of size at least 3 is contained in one part. Conversely, any subset of a single part is a general position set. \square

Lemma 2. Fix $\alpha \in (1, 2)$. For all sufficiently large positive integers m , with $n = \lfloor \alpha m \rfloor$, the polynomial $\psi(K_{m,n}; x)$ is unimodal.

Proof. For $k \geq 3$, put

$$b_k = \binom{m}{k} + \binom{n}{k}.$$

The correct adjacent difference is

$$b_{k+1} - b_k = \frac{\binom{m}{k}(m - 2k - 1) + \binom{n}{k}(n - 2k - 1)}{k + 1}. \quad (1)$$

If $k < (m - 1)/2$, both summands in (1) are positive, while if $k > (n - 1)/2$, both are non-positive and at least one is negative whenever b_k is nonzero. It remains to treat

$$\frac{m - 1}{2} \leq k < \frac{n - 1}{2}.$$

Since $n/m \rightarrow \alpha < 2$, this interval is contained in $k < m$ for all sufficiently large m . In this interval $n - 2k - 1 \geq 1$ and $2k + 1 - m < 2m$, while

$$\frac{\binom{n}{k}}{\binom{m}{k}} = \prod_{j=0}^{k-1} \frac{n - j}{m - j} \geq \left(\frac{n}{m} \right)^k.$$

For large m the last expression dominates $2m$, uniformly in the present range because $k \geq (m - 1)/2$ and n/m is bounded away from 1. Hence

$$\binom{n}{k}(n - 2k - 1) > \binom{m}{k}(2k + 1 - m),$$

and so $b_{k+1} > b_k$ throughout the middle range. Thus $(b_k)_{k \geq 3}$ is nondecreasing up to the middle of the larger part and nonincreasing afterwards. Finally,

$$\binom{m+n}{2} = O(m^2), \quad b_3 = \binom{m}{3} + \binom{n}{3} \asymp m^3,$$

so $1, N, \binom{N}{2}, b_3$ are eventually increasing. The full coefficient sequence is therefore unimodal. \square

3 The corona of a complete bipartite graph

Let $H_{m,n} = K_{m,n} \circ K_1$. Let the partite sets of $K_{m,n}$ be A and B , with $|A| = m$ and $|B| = n$. For each original vertex v write v' for the new pendent neighbor attached to v .

Lemma 3. *Let $S \subseteq V(H_{m,n})$ with $|S| \geq 3$. Then S is a general position set if and only if exactly one of the following holds.*

- (i) S consists only of pendent vertices.
- (ii) S contains at least one original vertex of A , contains no original vertex of B , contains at most one pendent vertex from the B -side, and contains at most one vertex from each pair $\{a, a'\}$ with $a \in A$.
- (iii) The symmetric condition obtained from (ii) by interchanging A and B holds.

Proof. All pendent vertices form a general position set, because a pendent vertex has degree one and therefore cannot be an internal vertex of a geodesic between two other pendent vertices.

Suppose next that S contains an original vertex $a \in A$. If S also contains an original vertex $b \in B$, then no third vertex can be added: for any third vertex z , either a lies on a geodesic between b and z , or b lies on a geodesic between a and z . Hence a general position set of size at least 3 cannot contain original vertices from both sides.

Still assuming that S contains an original vertex of A , two further restrictions are forced. First, S cannot contain both a and a' , because a lies on every geodesic from a' to any vertex not equal to a' . Thus at most one vertex from each pair $\{a, a'\}$ can be selected. Second, if two pendent vertices b'_1, b'_2 from the B -side were selected, then any selected original vertex $a \in A$ lies on a shortest path

$$b'_1, b_1, a, b_2, b'_2,$$

contradicting the general position condition. Therefore at most one pendent vertex from the B -side can be selected.

Conversely, any set satisfying (ii) is in general position. Indeed, a geodesic between two selected vertices on the A -side uses only unselected original vertices from B and possibly the unselected support vertices of selected pendants. A geodesic from the unique possible selected B -side pendent vertex to a selected A -side vertex has only its support in B and possibly an unselected support in A as internal vertices. Hence no selected vertex is an internal vertex of such a geodesic. The proof of (iii) is symmetric. \square

Lemma 4. *For $m, n \geq 1$, put $N = m + n$. Then*

$$\psi(H_{m,n}; x) = 1 + 2Nx + \binom{2N}{2}x^2 + \sum_{k=3}^N c_k x^k,$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} c_k &= \binom{N}{k} + (2^k - 1) \left(\binom{m}{k} + \binom{n}{k} \right) \\ &\quad + (2^{k-1} - 1) \left(n \binom{m}{k-1} + m \binom{n}{k-1} \right). \end{aligned}$$

Proof. The terms $1 + 2Nx + \binom{2N}{2}x^2$ count all sets of size at most 2. For $k \geq 3$, use Lemma 3. The all-pendent case contributes $\binom{N}{k}$. If a set contains at least one original vertex from A , then for each $a \in A$ one may choose none, a' , or a , but at least one original A -vertex must be chosen;

this gives $(1 + 2x)^m - (1 + x)^m$. One may also choose at most one pendent vertex from the B -side, giving the factor $1 + nx$. Thus the A -original case contributes

$$((1 + 2x)^m - (1 + x)^m)(1 + nx).$$

The symmetric case contributes

$$((1 + 2x)^n - (1 + x)^n)(1 + mx).$$

Adding the all-pendent contribution $(1 + x)^N$ and extracting coefficients gives the stated formula. \square

4 The smallest complete bipartite counterexample

For $K_{36,51}$, Lemma 1 gives

$$\psi(K_{36,51}; x) = 1 + 87x + \binom{87}{2}x^2 + \sum_{k=3}^{51} \left(\binom{36}{k} + \binom{51}{k} \right) x^k.$$

An exact computation shows that its coefficients increase up to $k = 25$ and then decrease. Near the peak,

$$a_{24} = 229593165079600, \quad a_{25} = 247959867279348, \quad a_{26} = 247959520660908.$$

Thus $\psi(K_{36,51}; x)$ is unimodal.

For the corona, Lemma 4 gives the following exact coefficients:

$$\begin{aligned} c_{38} &= 13152111124967500512820050, \\ c_{39} &= 13124055700902640853399950, \\ c_{40} &= 13182964228382738350848210. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore

$$c_{38} > c_{39} < c_{40},$$

so $\psi(K_{36,51} \circ K_1; x)$ is not unimodal. The exhaustive finite minimality assertion in Theorem 1 is verified by the exact C++17 program in Appendix A, which uses arbitrary-precision integer arithmetic and checks all pairs $1 \leq m \leq n$ with $m + n \leq 87$.

5 The asymptotic slope interval

We now prove Theorem 2. Fix a real number $\alpha \in (1, 2)$ and put

$$n = \alpha m, \quad k = \beta m + t, \quad t = O(\log m),$$

where $1 < \beta < \alpha$. In the range $m + 1 < k < n$, Lemma 4 has two main terms,

$$U_k = \binom{(1 + \alpha)m}{k}, \quad V_k = 2^{k-1}m \binom{\alpha m}{k-1}.$$

The remaining nonzero term involving $\binom{n}{k}$ is negligible compared with V_k , since

$$\frac{2^k \binom{n}{k}}{V_k} = \frac{2(n - k + 1)}{mk} = O\left(\frac{1}{m}\right).$$

The terms caused by replacing 2^k and 2^{k-1} by $2^k - 1$ and $2^{k-1} - 1$ are exponentially smaller. Hence

$$c_k = U_k + V_k \left(1 + O\left(\frac{1}{m}\right)\right) \quad (2)$$

uniformly for $k = \beta m + O(\log m)$.

The exponential orders of U_k and V_k are balanced by

$$F_\alpha(\beta) := (1 + \alpha)\mathcal{H}\left(\frac{\beta}{1 + \alpha}\right) - \beta \log 2 - \alpha\mathcal{H}\left(\frac{\beta}{\alpha}\right) = 0. \quad (3)$$

Put

$$x = \alpha - \beta.$$

Then (3) is equivalent to $G_\alpha(x) = 0$, where

$$G_\alpha(x) = (1 + \alpha) \log(1 + \alpha) - \alpha \log \alpha + x \log x - (1 + x) \log(1 + x) - (\alpha - x) \log 2. \quad (4)$$

Moreover,

$$p = \frac{2(\alpha - \beta)}{\beta} = \frac{2x}{\alpha - x}, \quad q = \frac{1 + \alpha - \beta}{\beta} = \frac{1 + x}{\alpha - x}.$$

Here p and q are the limiting adjacent ratios

$$\frac{V_{k+1}}{V_k} \rightarrow p, \quad \frac{U_{k+1}}{U_k} \rightarrow q.$$

The condition $0 < p < 1 < q$ is equivalent to

$$\frac{\alpha - 1}{2} < x < \frac{\alpha}{3}. \quad (5)$$

On this interval,

$$\frac{\partial G_\alpha}{\partial x} = \log \frac{2x}{1 + x} < 0,$$

so G_α is strictly decreasing in x . Consequently, a solution satisfying (5) exists if and only if

$$G_\alpha\left(\frac{\alpha - 1}{2}\right) > 0 \quad \text{and} \quad G_\alpha\left(\frac{\alpha}{3}\right) < 0.$$

These two endpoint functions are exactly

$$\Phi_+(\alpha) = G_\alpha\left(\frac{\alpha - 1}{2}\right), \quad \Phi_-(\alpha) = G_\alpha\left(\frac{\alpha}{3}\right).$$

Lemma 5. *The functions Φ_- and Φ_+ are strictly decreasing on $(1, 2)$. Each has one and only one root in $(1, 2)$.*

Proof. Differentiating along $x = (\alpha - 1)/2$ gives

$$\Phi'_+(\alpha) = \log \frac{1 + \alpha}{2\alpha} + \frac{1}{2} \log \frac{2(\alpha - 1)}{\alpha + 1}.$$

This is negative because

$$\left(\frac{1 + \alpha}{2\alpha}\right)^2 \frac{2(\alpha - 1)}{\alpha + 1} = \frac{\alpha^2 - 1}{2\alpha^2} < 1.$$

Similarly, along $x = \alpha/3$,

$$\Phi'_-(\alpha) = \log \frac{1 + \alpha}{2\alpha} + \frac{1}{3} \log \frac{2\alpha}{\alpha + 3}.$$

This is negative because

$$\left(\frac{1+\alpha}{2\alpha}\right)^3 \frac{2\alpha}{\alpha+3} < 1,$$

equivalently

$$(1+\alpha)^3 < 4\alpha^2(\alpha+3),$$

which holds for $1 < \alpha < 2$.

The endpoint signs are

$$\lim_{\alpha \downarrow 1} \Phi_+(\alpha) = \log 2 > 0, \quad \Phi_+(2) = \frac{1}{2} \log \frac{27}{32} < 0,$$

and

$$\lim_{\alpha \downarrow 1} \Phi_-(\alpha) = \log \frac{3}{2^{4/3}} > 0, \quad \Phi_-(2) = \frac{1}{3} \log \frac{3^{12}}{2^{855}} < 0.$$

Strict monotonicity gives the asserted unique roots. \square

For reference, direct high-precision interval evaluation gives

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi_-(1.60697583486391) &> 0, & \Phi_-(1.60697583486392) &< 0, \\ \Phi_+(1.83212055954893) &> 0, & \Phi_+(1.83212055954894) &< 0. \end{aligned}$$

Thus the displayed decimal values of α_- and α_+ follow.

Fix now a rational $\alpha \in (\alpha_-, \alpha_+)$. Let x be the unique solution of $G_\alpha(x) = 0$ in (5), and set

$$\beta = \alpha - x, \quad p = \frac{2x}{\alpha - x}, \quad q = \frac{1+x}{\alpha - x}.$$

Then $0 < p < 1 < q$.

Lemma 6. For $k = \beta m + t$ with $t = O(\log m)$,

$$\frac{U_k}{V_k} = C_{\alpha,\beta} m^{-1} \left(\frac{q}{p}\right)^t \left(1 + O\left(\frac{(\log m)^2}{m}\right)\right),$$

where

$$C_{\alpha,\beta} = p \sqrt{\frac{(\alpha - \beta)(1 + \alpha)}{\alpha(1 + \alpha - \beta)}}.$$

Proof. Apply Stirling's formula uniformly for $t = O(\log m)$ to

$$U_k = \binom{(1+\alpha)m}{\beta m + t}$$

and

$$V_k = 2^{\beta m + t - 1} m \binom{\alpha m}{\beta m + t - 1}.$$

The equation $F_\alpha(\beta) = 0$ cancels the exponential factor of order m . The adjacent-ratio contribution as t varies is $(q/p)^t$. The shift from k to $k-1$ in the second binomial contributes the factor p , the Gaussian prefactors contribute

$$\sqrt{\frac{(\alpha - \beta)(1 + \alpha)}{\alpha(1 + \alpha - \beta)}},$$

and the explicit factor m in V_k contributes m^{-1} . \square

Lemma 7. *Let $A > 0$, $B \in \mathbb{R}$, $D \geq 1$ be an integer, and let $I \subset (0, 1)$ be a nonempty open interval. Then there are infinitely many multiples m of D such that*

$$\{A \log m + Bm\} \in I.$$

Proof. Write $m = Dr$. If DB is irrational, Weyl's criterion applies. For every nonzero integer h ,

$$\sum_{r \leq R} e^{2\pi i h(A \log(Dr) + BDr)} = D^{2\pi i h A} \sum_{r \leq R} r^{2\pi i h A} e^{2\pi i h DBr} = o(R),$$

where the final estimate follows by summation by parts from the bounded partial sums of $e^{2\pi i h DBr}$. Thus the sequence is equidistributed modulo 1.

If DB is rational, restrict r to a residue class modulo its denominator, so that the linear term is constant modulo 1. It remains to note that $\{A \log r\}$ is dense modulo 1 along any residue class: for any target interval, the corresponding intervals for r have lengths tending to infinity, and hence eventually contain members of the chosen residue class. \square

Lemma 8. *For every rational $\alpha \in (\alpha_-, \alpha_+)$ there are infinitely many positive integers m , with $n = \alpha m$ integral, such that the coefficients of $\psi(K_{m,n} \circ K_1; x)$ have a strict local valley*

$$c_{k-1} > c_k < c_{k+1}$$

for some k .

Proof. Let D be the denominator of α . We only use multiples of D , so $n = \alpha m$ is an integer. Define $R_k = U_k/V_k$. For the two main terms,

$$\frac{U_{k+1}}{U_k} \rightarrow q > 1, \quad \frac{V_{k+1}}{V_k} \rightarrow p < 1.$$

The main-term inequalities

$$U_{k-1} + V_{k-1} > U_k + V_k < U_{k+1} + V_{k+1}$$

are equivalent, up to an error tending to 0 uniformly in the present window, to

$$R_k \in I := \left(\frac{1-p}{q-1}, \frac{p^{-1}-1}{1-q^{-1}} \right).$$

This interval is nonempty, since its upper endpoint is (q/p) times its lower endpoint and $q/p > 1$.

Choose a compact subinterval $J \Subset I$. Put

$$L = \log(q/p), \quad A = \frac{1}{L},$$

and define

$$y_m = \beta m + A(\log m - \log C_{\alpha, \beta}) + \theta, \quad k = \lfloor y_m \rfloor.$$

By Lemma 6,

$$R_k = \exp(L(\theta - \{y_m\})) \left(1 + O\left(\frac{(\log m)^2}{m}\right) \right).$$

Choose θ so that the inverse image of J under $u \mapsto \exp(L(\theta - u))$ contains a nonempty open interval. Lemma 7 gives infinitely many multiples m of D for which $\{y_m\}$ lies in this interval. For these m , and all sufficiently large among them, $R_k \in J$.

Because J is compactly contained in I , the main-term valley has a fixed positive margin proportional to V_k . The estimate (2), applied uniformly to $k-1, k, k+1$, shows that the smaller terms in the exact coefficient c_j are only $O(V_j/m)$ in the relevant window. Hence the strict local valley persists for the true coefficients c_{k-1}, c_k, c_{k+1} . \square

Proof of Theorem 2. Let $\alpha \in (\alpha_-, \alpha_+) \cap \mathbb{Q}$. By Lemma 8, there are infinitely many m for which $\psi(K_{m, \alpha m} \circ K_1; x)$ is not unimodal. By Lemma 2, after discarding finitely many of these m , the base polynomial $\psi(K_{m, \alpha m}; x)$ is unimodal. This proves the theorem. \square

6 Eventual unimodality outside the slope interval

We now prove Theorem 3(b). The next lemma is the uniform estimate used to separate the two dominant terms in Lemma 4.

Lemma 9 (uniform Stirling epsilon lemma). *Fix $1 < \alpha < 2$ and put $n = \alpha m$. For $0 < k < n$ write $\beta = k/m$ and set*

$$P_k = \binom{(1+\alpha)m}{k}, \quad Q_k = (2^{k-1} - 1)m \binom{\alpha m}{k-1}.$$

Let $D_k = c_k - P_k - Q_k$, where c_k denotes the coefficient in Lemma 4. Define

$$A_\alpha(\beta) = (1+\alpha)\mathcal{H}\left(\frac{\beta}{1+\alpha}\right), \quad B_\alpha(\beta) = \beta \log 2 + \alpha\mathcal{H}\left(\frac{\beta}{\alpha}\right),$$

and

$$\rho_A(\beta) = \frac{1+\alpha-\beta}{\beta}, \quad \rho_B(\beta) = \frac{2(\alpha-\beta)}{\beta}.$$

Then the following estimates hold.

(i) For every compact interval $K \subset (0, \alpha)$, uniformly for $k/m \in K$,

$$\log P_k = mA_\alpha(\beta) + O_K(\log m), \quad \log Q_k = mB_\alpha(\beta) + O_K(\log m),$$

and

$$\frac{P_{k+1}}{P_k} = \rho_A(\beta) + O_K(m^{-1}), \quad \frac{Q_{k+1}}{Q_k} = \rho_B(\beta) + O_K(m^{-1}).$$

(ii) Uniformly for $k/m \in K$,

$$D_k = O_K\left(\frac{Q_k}{m}\right) + O_K((P_k + Q_k)e^{-\eta_K m})$$

for some constant $\eta_K > 0$. Consequently, if $A_\alpha \geq B_\alpha + \varepsilon$ on K , then $c_k = P_k(1 + O_K(e^{-\varepsilon' m}))$ on K for some $\varepsilon' > 0$; if $B_\alpha \geq A_\alpha + \varepsilon$ on K , then $c_k = Q_k(1 + O_K(m^{-1}))$ on K .

(iii) If, on K , both ρ_A and ρ_B are at least $1 + \varepsilon$, then for all sufficiently large m one has $c_{k+1} > c_k$ for every k with $k/m \in K$. If, on K , both ρ_A and ρ_B are at most $1 - \varepsilon$, then for all sufficiently large m one has $c_{k+1} < c_k$ for every such k .

(iv) More generally, if $A_\alpha \geq B_\alpha + \varepsilon$ on K and $\rho_A \geq 1 + \varepsilon$ on K , then $c_{k+1} > c_k$ on K for all sufficiently large m ; if $A_\alpha \geq B_\alpha + \varepsilon$ and $\rho_A \leq 1 - \varepsilon$, then $c_{k+1} < c_k$ on K for all sufficiently large m . The same statements hold with A_α, P_k, ρ_A replaced by B_α, Q_k, ρ_B .

Proof. We use Stirling's formula in the form

$$\binom{\lambda m}{u\lambda m + O(1)} = \exp\{\lambda m\mathcal{H}(u) + O_K(\log m)\},$$

uniformly when λ ranges over a fixed compact subset of $(0, \infty)$ and u ranges over a compact subinterval of $(0, 1)$. This gives the two logarithmic estimates in (i). The adjacent-ratio estimates in (i) are exact ratio computations:

$$\frac{P_{k+1}}{P_k} = \frac{(1+\alpha)m - k}{k+1} = \frac{1+\alpha-\beta}{\beta} + O_K(m^{-1}),$$

and

$$\frac{Q_{k+1}}{Q_k} = \frac{2^k - 1}{2^{k-1} - 1} \cdot \frac{\alpha m - k + 1}{k} = \frac{2(\alpha - \beta)}{\beta} + O_K(m^{-1}).$$

It remains to bound the terms not included in $P_k + Q_k$. The other term coming from the larger part satisfies

$$\frac{(2^k - 1) \binom{\alpha m}{k}}{Q_k} = \frac{2^k - 1}{2^{k-1} - 1} \cdot \frac{\alpha m - k + 1}{mk} = O_K(m^{-1}).$$

The terms coming from the smaller part have exponential rate

$$S(\beta) = \beta \log 2 + \mathcal{H}(\beta) \quad (0 < \beta < 1),$$

and are absent for $\beta > 1$. On $K \cap (0, 1]$ we have

$$B_\alpha(\beta) - S(\beta) = \alpha \mathcal{H}(\beta/\alpha) - \mathcal{H}(\beta) > 0,$$

because, for fixed β , the derivative of $u \mapsto u \mathcal{H}(\beta/u)$ is $-\log(1 - \beta/u) > 0$. Compactness gives a positive minimum away from zero. This proves (ii).

For (iii), write

$$c_{k+1} - c_k = P_k \left(\frac{P_{k+1}}{P_k} - 1 \right) + Q_k \left(\frac{Q_{k+1}}{Q_k} - 1 \right) + (D_{k+1} - D_k).$$

By (ii), $D_{k+1} - D_k = o_K(P_k + Q_k)$ uniformly on K . Hence, if both limiting ratios are bounded above or below 1 by a fixed positive margin, the sign is the common sign of the two displayed main contributions. Part (iv) follows in the same way from (ii), because under an exponential separation only the dominant summand can affect the sign. \square

Proof of Theorem 3. Part (a) is Theorem 2. We prove part (b). Put

$$\beta_B = \frac{2\alpha}{3}, \quad \beta_A = \frac{1 + \alpha}{2}.$$

The limiting adjacent ratios in Lemma 9 show that the larger-part term Q_k increases before $\beta_B m$ and decreases after $\beta_B m$, while the all-pendent term P_k increases before $\beta_A m$ and decreases after $\beta_A m$. Since $1 < \alpha < 2$, we have

$$\beta_B < \beta_A.$$

The equation $A_\alpha(\beta) = B_\alpha(\beta)$ is the same as $G_\alpha(x) = 0$ with $x = \alpha - \beta$. There is a unique crossing $\beta_0 \in (0, \alpha)$ other than the boundary point $\beta = 0$: indeed, for $F_\alpha = A_\alpha - B_\alpha$ one has

$$F'_\alpha(\beta) = \log \frac{1 + \alpha - \beta}{2(\alpha - \beta)},$$

so F_α decreases on $(0, \alpha - 1)$ and increases on $(\alpha - 1, \alpha)$; moreover $F_\alpha(\beta) < 0$ for all sufficiently small positive β , while $F_\alpha(\alpha) > 0$. The endpoint analysis in Section 5 gives the following location of this crossing:

$$\begin{cases} \beta_0 < \beta_B, & 1 < \alpha < \alpha_-, \\ \beta_B < \beta_0 < \beta_A, & \alpha_- < \alpha < \alpha_+, \\ \beta_A < \beta_0, & \alpha_+ < \alpha < 2. \end{cases}$$

Only the first and third cases are needed for part (b).

First suppose $1 < \alpha < \alpha_-$. Then

$$\beta_0 < \beta_B < \beta_A.$$

Choose $\eta > 0$ so small that these three numbers remain separated by at least 4η . On compact subintervals lying to the left of $\beta_0 - \eta$, the rate B_α exceeds A_α by a fixed positive amount and $\rho_B > 1$ by a fixed positive amount; Lemma 9(iv) gives $c_{k+1} > c_k$ there. On the crossing window $[\beta_0 - \eta, \beta_0 + \eta]$, both ρ_A and ρ_B are still larger than 1 by a fixed margin, so Lemma 9(iii) again gives $c_{k+1} > c_k$. On compact subintervals from the right of this window up to $\beta_A - \eta$, the rate A_α dominates and $\rho_A > 1$, so the coefficients keep increasing. On compact subintervals to the right of $\beta_A + \eta$, the rate A_α dominates and $\rho_A < 1$, so the coefficients decrease.

It remains only to handle a small central neighborhood of $\beta_A m$. There the rate A_α exceeds B_α by a fixed positive amount, so $c_k = P_k(1 + O(e^{-\gamma m}))$ for some $\gamma > 0$. The exact ratios

$$\frac{P_{k+1}}{P_k} = \frac{(1 + \alpha)m - k}{k + 1}$$

are strictly decreasing in k , and therefore P_k has one peak, possibly with a two-term plateau. Away from the possible central equality $P_{k+1} = P_k$, the quantity $|P_{k+1}/P_k - 1|$ is at least a constant multiple of $1/m$, which is much larger than $e^{-\gamma m}$. Hence $c_{k+1} - c_k$ has the same sign pattern as $P_{k+1} - P_k$, apart from the harmless possible resolution of a two-term plateau. Combining this with the sign control outside the neighborhood gives a single eventual peak.

Now suppose $\alpha_+ < \alpha < 2$. Then

$$\beta_B < \beta_A < \beta_0.$$

Choose $\eta > 0$ separating these three points. Up to the Q -peak, the rate B_α dominates and $\rho_B > 1$, so the coefficients increase. Near the exact Q -peak, write

$$W_k = (2^k - 1) \binom{\alpha m}{k}, \quad T_k = Q_k + W_k.$$

Then

$$\frac{W_k}{Q_k} = \frac{2^k - 1}{2^{k-1} - 1} \cdot \frac{\alpha m - k + 1}{mk} = O(m^{-1}),$$

and this ratio is strictly decreasing in k . Also

$$\frac{Q_{k+1}}{Q_k} = \left(2 + \frac{1}{2^{k-1} - 1}\right) \frac{\alpha m - k + 1}{k}$$

is strictly decreasing in k and crosses 1 once, possibly with a two-term plateau. It follows, by the displayed quotient formulas, that the adjacent quotient T_{k+1}/T_k is also decreasing in the central $O(1)$ peak window for all sufficiently large m ; outside that window the sign has already been fixed by Lemma 9. Thus the dominant larger-part contribution has a single peak. All remaining terms are exponentially smaller there and cannot create a descent followed later by an ascent. From the right of the Q -peak to the crossing window, B_α still dominates and $\rho_B < 1$, so the coefficients decrease. On the crossing window around β_0 , both ρ_A and ρ_B are less than 1 by a fixed margin, so Lemma 9(iii) gives $c_{k+1} < c_k$. After the crossing, A_α dominates and is already decreasing. Thus no increase can occur after the first peak.

Finally choose a small fixed $\delta > 0$ outside the compact intervals considered above. For $3 \leq k \leq \delta m$, every nonzero summand in the exact formula for c_k is increasing; for $(\alpha - \delta)m \leq k \leq \alpha m$, every nonzero summand is decreasing. This follows directly from the exact adjacent ratios. Moreover c_0, c_1, c_2, c_3 are increasing for large m . Combining the initial tail, the central analysis, and the terminal tail proves eventual unimodality outside the interval. \square

A Exact verification code

The following C++17 program verifies Theorem 1. It uses `boost::multiprecision::cpp_int`, so all integer coefficients are exact. The expected output is displayed after the program.

```

#include <bits/stdc++.h>
#include <boost/multiprecision/cpp_int.hpp>
using namespace std;
using boost::multiprecision::cpp_int;

cpp_int C(int n, int k) {
    if (k < 0 || k > n) return 0;
    if (k > n-k) k = n-k;
    cpp_int r = 1;
    for (int i = 1; i <= k; i++) {
        r *= (n-k+i);
        r /= i;
    }
    return r;
}

cpp_int pow2(int k) { return cpp_int(1) << k; }

vector<cpp_int> base_poly(int m, int n) {
    int L = max(m,n), N = m+n;
    vector<cpp_int> a(L+1);
    a[0] = 1;
    if (L >= 1) a[1] = N;
    if (L >= 2) a[2] = C(N,2);
    for (int k = 3; k <= L; k++) a[k] = C(m,k) + C(n,k);
    return a;
}

vector<cpp_int> corona_poly(int m, int n) {
    int N = m+n;
    vector<cpp_int> a(N+1);
    a[0] = 1;
    a[1] = 2*N;
    a[2] = C(2*N,2);
    for (int k = 3; k <= N; k++) {
        a[k] = C(N,k)
            + (pow2(k)-1)*(C(m,k)+C(n,k))
            + (pow2(k-1)-1)*(n*C(m,k-1)+m*C(n,k-1));
    }
    return a;
}

bool unimodal(const vector<cpp_int>& a) {
    int i = 0, N = (int)a.size();
    while (i+1 < N && a[i] <= a[i+1]) i++;
    while (i+1 < N && a[i] >= a[i+1]) i++;
    return i == N-1;
}

int main() {
    int m = 36, n = 51;
    auto b = base_poly(m,n);
    auto c = corona_poly(m,n);

    cout << "Base unimodal: " << unimodal(b) << "\n";
    cout << "Corona unimodal: " << unimodal(c) << "\n";
}

```

```

cout << "b[24] = " << b[24] << "\n";
cout << "b[25] = " << b[25] << "\n";
cout << "b[26] = " << b[26] << "\n";

cout << "c[38] = " << c[38] << "\n";
cout << "c[39] = " << c[39] << "\n";
cout << "c[40] = " << c[40] << "\n";

int count87 = 0;
for (int N = 2; N <= 87; N++) {
    for (int a = 1; a <= N/2; a++) {
        int d = N-a;
        bool property = unimodal(base_poly(a,d))
            && !unimodal(corona_poly(a,d));
        if (property) {
            cout << "Example: N=" << N << " pair=(" << a << ", " << d << ")\n";
            if (N < 87) return 1;
            if (N == 87) count87++;
        }
    }
}
cout << "Number of examples with N=87: " << count87 << "\n";
}

```

The output is:

```

Base unimodal: 1
Corona unimodal: 0
b[24] = 229593165079600
b[25] = 247959867279348
b[26] = 247959520660908
c[38] = 13152111124967500512820050
c[39] = 13124055700902640853399950
c[40] = 13182964228382738350848210
Example: N=87 pair=(36,51)
Number of examples with N=87: 1

```

References

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- [2] B. A. Rather, Explicit formulas and unimodality phenomena for general position polynomials, arXiv:2603.06930v2, 2026. doi:10.48550/arXiv.2603.06930.